

Recommended citation: Roseiro, L. M., Ferreira, P., & Amaro, P. (2019). Project in mechanical engineering, an experience in the involvement of students in the development of biomechanical devices in partnership with paralympic athletes. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 926-935). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656599.

Project in Mechanical Engineering, an Experience in the Involvement of students in the Development of Biomechanical Devices in Partnership with Paralympic Athletes

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Conference Key Areas: Diversity in Engineering Education

Keywords: Teaching Mechanical Engineering, Mechanical Project Development, Biomechanical Devices in Mechanical Engineering

ABSTRACT

In cycling sport, motor-disabled athletes can only develop their practice if they have compensation devices allowing them to a practice with comfort, safety and performance. However, this type of devices does not exist in a standardized way, and should be developed on a tailor basis. The challenge of collaborating in the development of these biomechanical devices can be placed in engineering schools, involving students in their development, learning a set of important competencies. This work presents a collaborative experience among several students from mechanical engineering, the most important field in this context, and two adapted cycling athletes, from the Portuguese National Team. Students participation was inserted in the curricular unit of Project, part of the degree in mechanical engineering, and real biomechanical prototypes have been developed and implemented. The biomechanics devices radically changed the practice of cycling by the athletes, highlighting the importance of the school in the context of its social involvement. A survey has been defined for the students involved, showing that this kind of collaborative work, with a need to go out of school and develop a solution to be implemented in this type of real situation, allowed them to acquire a set of important skills in the context of their engineering apprenticeship.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The history of civilization can be associated with the history of engineering. The civilizations considered as more advanced are in general by their achievements in this domain of knowledge and development. And it was so over the time, being simply to see the testament left in the cities and pyramids of the Mayas, Incas and Aztecs, the acropolis of Athens, the great wall of China, among many other examples. The man began to be an engineer when he dared to stop being quadrupedal. At this stage of development, he extended the brain to two of its members, hence superior and fundamental in the art of developing and doing.

Several definitions of what is engineering can be found in literature, normally associated with the problem-solving challenge. S. E. Lindsay (1920) defined engineering as “the practice of safe and economic application of the scientific laws governing the forces and materials of nature by means of organization, design and construction, for the general benefit of mankind”. James Kip Finch (1960) defines the engineer as a maker of history.

1.1 A Mechanical Engineer

In many situations, the mechanical engineer is perhaps wrongly associated only with automobiles and auto shops. The automotive industry is just one example of the mechanical engineer's domain. Traditionally, the metallurgical sector has been the great employer of this profile of engineers; however, its activity may cover various sectors of activity, which include the textile industry, agricultural equipment, chemical and petroleum industry, aeronautics, molds and glass, the design of industrial buildings and facilities, electronics and computers, banking and insurance, among many others.

Mechanical engineering can be framed at the level of the development / processing of a product, it can be said that its activity takes place in stages of an essentially technical nature, but where the competences linked to the management and administration also play an important role and where the ability to exchange ideas and results is vital. Typically, engineers communicate both upstream and downstream, writing proposals and technical reports, making presentations and interacting with elements of their team or external teams. In this particular, language at the technical level, where sketches, drawings, graphs and data tables prevail, is reason enough for the mechanical engineer to develop skills in the capacity of teamwork, writing and communication, but clearly and concise.

Methodology and organization are important characteristics for a mechanical engineer who, must possess logical reasoning skills, consistently understand of physical phenomena, perform mathematical operations correctly, know how to idealize and analyze problems but, more and more, manage and present simple, practical and effective solutions. The mechanical engineer performs part of his work integrating teams typically composed of engineers from various fields, depending on the type of product under analysis or development. However, their dialogue is not just at the level of colleagues from other specialties.

1.2 A Mechanical Engineer in Biomechanics

Recently, the participation of the mechanical engineers in the health area has been emerging. It's true that they already participated in some activities, like the management and maintenance of hospital equipment, but the evolution of the dialogue between mechanical engineers and health professionals has been growing in the last decades, highlighting the concept of biomechanics, which derives morphologically from the grouping of "bio" (biological, living beings) with mechanics, and can be defined as the application of the principles of mechanics to living beings. Biomechanics was defined by Hay (1978) as "The science that studies the internal and external forces in the human body and the effects produced by these forces". Biomechanics can be connected to occupational activities, sports, musculoskeletal systems, orthopedic, rehabilitation, cardiovascular, biomaterials, among many others, all with a strong connection to mechanical engineering.

It is clear that the role of a mechanical engineer in this field of applications is extremely important. Here are two statements retained by the author in meetings with medical people, illustrating the significance of knowledge in mechanical engineering for other professionals, particularly in the field of health:

"I believe that if I had a mechanical engineer in the surgery room with me, in certain situations I would be more successful," an orthopedic doctor;

"It would be great to have a mechanical engineer with me who could help develop specific support products for some of my patients" a physician in physical medicine and rehabilitation.

One of the strongest participations of mechanical engineers is in the rehabilitation context, defined by World Health Organization (WHO) as "the use of all means necessary to reduce the impact of disabling situations and enable disabled individuals to achieve complete social integration." This definition, taken from the White Paper on Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation in Europe, focuses as an important and emerging goal the concept of social participation, highlighting the needs of individuals with disabilities, in order to eliminate social barriers to participation, both socially and vocationally. The term "Technical Aids", also defined as "Support Products", can be designated as the set of means indispensable for the autonomy and integration of persons with disabilities or motor handicaps, aiming to attenuate or compensate for this disability or limitation and to allow their daily activities and participation in school, professional and social life.

1.3 Teaching Mechanical Engineering

Mechanical engineering has been more focused on engineering science curriculum, that does not include some important practical elements. The courses mainly with strong analytical approach can led students to a gap in design development. Even both, analytical and design thinking are important, they strongly differ [1, 2], and design are more connected to the main activities of a mechanical engineer [3], particularly to create solutions in a creative and innovative way.

Given that the mechanical engineer is perhaps the most diverse of the engineering domain, it will be important to prepare the student for the development of design works with interconnection with other fields, with challenges that motivate him to develop the work, acquiring a set of concept knowledge, skills and attitude toward engineering. Since a mechanical engineer can play a major role in the medical field, and particularly in biomechanics, mechanical engineer students can also develop applied learning work in this field, allowing them to have the opportunity to contact with this reality, develop and improve teamworking skills and broaden other horizons.

This work presents a collaborative experience among several students from mechanical engineering and two adapted cycling athletes, one handless and other trans tibial amputee, from the Portuguese National Team, supervised by the teachers of project and in collaboration with some companies. The participation of the engineering students was inserted in the curricular unit of Project, part of the degree in mechanical engineering, and real biomechanical prototypes have been developed in order to provide safety, comfort and performance to the adapted athlete, allowing them to practice cycling. The projects have gradually been optimized, thus involving a sequence of project developments and several different students. The collaborative work with these athletes has been developed over several years, and some of the students are already included in the job market. In order to evaluate the importance of students' involvement in this type of project and the challenge of development, with a strong innovation and risk component, a survey was defined for the students, whose results are presented.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The project curriculum is an integral part of the 3rd year mechanical engineering course. It has a weight of 7 European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) and aims to develop students' ability to apply the knowledge acquired throughout the course. The unit also stimulates the capacity for analysis and critical/design thinking of students as well as their skills in organization, communication and teamwork. Wherever possible, the project work may be directed towards the development of functional prototypes and also carried out in collaboration with companies or other entities outside the school, looking for its implementation in a real context.

The case presented involves the participation of two athletes from the Portuguese National team of adapted cycling, the collaboration of some industrial entities, as well as the participation of the Portuguese cycling federation. The work begins with the development of a first prototype for a trans tibial amputee athlete. For this athlete, several optimizations of the devices have been developed by the students. Recently, also a handless athlete was involved in this collaboration, having been developed a prototype for his practice of adapted cycling.

The development of this type of project work required the use of several mechanical engineering tools, where the components of 3D modelling, computer-assisted design and manufacturing could be highlighted. Also, the skills at the level of mechanical

engineering concepts, especially the strength of materials and reverse engineering can be highlighted. Considering the limitations imposed by the physical conditions of the athletes, creativity were decisive tools for the development of applied solutions. Thus, the specifications of the work theme, methodology to follow and main objectives to be achieved are clearly defined in the initial presentation for students. The students were selected according to their motivation for the proposed work and abilities demonstrated within the curricular units considered relevant to the development of the project type.

Several students were involved in the presented project work. Normally in groups of two (individually in some particular cases), the students work collaboratively with the athlete and sometimes with the cycling team coaches, with the supervision and accompaniment of the project teachers. Some components of the development of functional prototypes were executed in partnership with two companies, in particular in the implementation of solutions in composite materials, allowing the contact with entities outside the school.

The pedagogical methodology used forced the students to a set of important activities in the context of learning in the application of the concepts associated with the project, with particular emphasis within:

- Predefined team meetings with the involved persons (teachers, athlete, coach, companies);
- Meeting reports prepared by the students;
- Identification of weaknesses and strengths in the evolution of the solution being developed;
- For each problem or difficulty, at least one solution must be presented by the students to overcome it.
- Present and discussion of the final solution with a project report.

2.1 Tibial Amputee Athlete and Prototypes

The National Team athlete (TP), suffered an accident that forced him to have a trans tibial amputation in his left leg. Lover of the sport, and with an unshakeable force and determination, after the adaptation to his prosthesis of walking, TP began to practice karate. However, it was the bike to set its Paralympic path.

The support given over the years to the athlete by the Coimbra Polytechnic – ISEC (School of Engineering) has led to the development of two main compensation devices in order to allow him to practice competitive cycling in safety and with the best level of performance possible, namely: a) Compensation Device - External Trans tibial Prosthesis; b) Compensation Device - Lateral Side Support.

The external trans tibial prosthesis, shown in figure 1, can be divided into three main sectors: longitudinal stem with coupling to the cup, "coupling foot" to the clip and consequently to the pedal and stem-foot connection. The longitudinal rod is composed of a carbon/kevlar tube with two aluminum machined terminals. One of these terminals allows attachment of the prosthesis to an össur® system, coupled to the amputated

area (stump) and the other terminal connects the stem of the coupling foot system to the strap, which is designed to have a useful virtual length equal to the athlete's foot. The stem-to-foot attachment system is composed by a set that integrates three synoblock positioned so as to allow adequate dynamic stiffness. This solution, with simple and innovative features allows an angular compensation in the athlete's pedalling, guaranteeing the protection of the knee joint. In addition, the accumulation of energy during the pedalling improves the performance of the athlete. Figure 1 shows the 3d model of the biomechanical system (a), the real prototype (b) and the tests implemented in real conditions. The development of the trans tibial prosthesis have been made in collaboration with a group of three students.

Fig. 1. External Trans tibial Prosthesis: a) 3D model; b) Real model; c) Test in real conditions.

Unfortunately, due to medical reasons, particularly for knee protection of the amputated leg, the athlete was forced to stop practicing cycling with both legs, and consequently stopped using the compensating device described above (trans tibial prosthesis), forcing the development of a new device to pedal with only one leg.

The figure 2 shows the first biomechanical model developed to pedal with one leg, based on an adjustable, trough support for the athlete's thigh. For this development a group of students have been involved.

Fig. 2. First Prototype for pedalling with one leg.

Following the optimization of the previous device, there was a project optimization with the involvement of another group of students, which led to a final prototype, shown in figure 3. With this prototype, the athlete participated in the Paralympic Games Rio2016, getting a sixth place.

Fig. 3. Final Prototype for pedalling with one leg: a) Real model; b) Participation in RIO2016.

2.2 Handless Athlete and Prototype

The National Team athlete (MF), was born with agenesis in the left hand, a congenital limitation translated by the absence of the hand. After the identification and characterization of the physical limitation of the athlete, the design of the device was centred on a fitting system, based on the concept of the docking pedal, composed of a set of structural elements, one of them adjustable, and which allows the athlete an adequate positioning in the bicycle, exert force in both directions, that is, push and pull the handlebar, increasing its performance and comfort, without compromising its safety, since in case of fall, the decoupling is guaranteed by the docking system.

The biomechanical device shown may be characterized by three parts, shown in figure 4, an arm-fitting prosthesis, an interface member and an adjustable handlebar attachment system.

Fig. 4. Handless Prototype for pedalling: a) Arm-fitting prosthesis; b) Interface system; c) Handlebar attachment system.

Fig. 4. Tests with the final prototype.

3 SURVEY EVALUATION

In order to acquire and analyse the feedback from the students, based on their learning experience of the involvement on these project themes and methodology, a survey have been prepared and sent to the students. The questionnaire was developed based in the work of Yu *et al.* (2012) [4]. All the questionnaire was anonymous and provide four main groups of questions, in the form of statements. For each affirmation, the students must answer selecting from four scores (1 - 4):

1 - Strongly disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Agree; 4 – Strongly Agree.

The group of affirmations, placed in the questionnaire as follow, have been answered by a total of five students. The survey, the mean scores and standard deviation, obtained for each statement, are described below.

A. Toward Learning procedures:

A.1 Participation in this project helps me to learning to learn - (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

A.2 Participation in this project helps me to learning to do – (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

A.3 Participation in this project gives me better Engagement and Reliability – (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

A.4 The project type, with a Paralympic Athlete improves my Self-confidence – (mean score $3,4 \pm 0,9$);

A.5 External connection with the Athlete was very important to my learning – (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

A.6 The project type, in a Taylor Basis, due to the athlete characteristics was a motivation factor for the work – (mean score $3,4 \pm 0,5$);

B. Some Engineering Concept Knowledge have been improved with my participation in this project, namely:

B.1 Physics and Math – (mean score $3,0 \pm 0,7$);

B.2 Materials and Process – (mean score $3,4 \pm 0,9$);

B.3 Modelling and Design – (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,9$);

B.4 Engineering in Society – (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

B.5 Professional and Ethical Responsibilities of engineers – (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

C. Some Engineering Skills have been improved with my participation in this project, namely:

C.1 Computer Aided Design – (mean score $3,0 \pm 0,7$);

C.2 Computer Aided Engineering – (mean score $3,2 \pm 0,8$);

C.3 Computer Aided Manufacturing – (mean score $3,0 \pm 0,7$);

C.4 Research Methodology – (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,5$);

C.5 Problem Definition - - (mean score $3,8 \pm 0,4$);

C.6 Teamwork in Engineering Projects – (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,9$);

C.7 Communication – (mean score $3,4 \pm 0,9$);

D. After my participation in this project, my attitudes toward engineering also involves:

D.1 Willing to improve mechanical engineering concept knowledge – (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,5$);

D.2 Willing to learn innovative concepts/ideas in mechanical engineering - - (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,5$);

D.3 Willing to learn concepts in other engineering domains – (mean score $3,4 \pm 0,5$);

D.4 My knowledge about the impact of engineering solutions on society – (mean score $3,6 \pm 0,5$);

D.5 My enthusiastic in knowledge/skills application in engineering practice – (mean score $4,0 \pm 0,0$);

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The students feedback showed that generally they have a strong satisfaction with the project developed. From the questionnaire it can be highlighted that all the students demonstrate their enthusiastic in knowledge and skills application in engineering practice, obtained from the project development.

Concerning the methodology used, the students strongly agree with the learning procedures associated with the type of project development.

The pedagogical methodology implemented with several predefined project team meeting, with the teachers accompanying the work, as well as with the athlete involved, his coach and the company that may collaborate with the work, played an important role in time management for the development of a solution, contributing to the students' understanding of the labour market, which is very demanding in this regard. As a methodology, the meetings always resulted in a minute of presentation and decisions taken, considered important in learning the record of the evolution of work and its path to the end. The meetings were also important in teamwork improvement.

As a methodology, students always presented the strengths and weaknesses identified in the solution under analysis (evolution of the prototype under development). An important aspect assumed in student teaching and supervision methodology was that for each problem or difficulty encountered in particular in the prototype development, the students should present at least one possible solution to overcome it, and if possible different paths to follow. After the conclusion of the work, and during their discussion, this aspect was verbally mentioned by the students as an excellent pedagogical methodology, which forced them not only to present identified difficulties, but also solutions to overcome them.

The engineering concept knowledge, and engineering skills have an agreement by all the students, with highlighting in understanding the role of engineering in society and the professional and ethical responsibilities, suggesting that the type of project developed contributed to this identification.

It can be stated that this kind of collaborative work, with the need to go out of school and develop a solution to be implemented in a real situation, allows the students to acquire a set of important skills in the context of their engineering apprenticeship.

Finally, the developed biomechanical devices radically changed the practice of cycling by both athletes. This aspect is also relevant, as it allowed the school to participate in the development of applied solutions that these athletes would probably not be able to achieve otherwise, highlighting the importance of engineering education institutions in the context of its social involvement.

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